

Law and Humanities Quarterly Reviews

Herlinda, E., Ningsih, S., & Rambe, I. N. (2023). Corruption Prevention at the Village Level: A Study of the Legal Cadre Training and Formation Model. *Law and Humanities Quarterly Reviews*, 2(2), 78-92.

ISSN 2827-9735

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1996.02.02.61

The online version of this article can be found at:
<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

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Corruption Prevention at the Village Level: A Study of the Legal Cadre Training and Formation Model

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Abstract

Corruption in the management of village finances is an action that can harm both the finances and the economy of the state or the village. Therefore, village officials must receive guidance on clean and corruption-free governance, collusion and nepotism. In this regard, the role of the community is needed to exercise social control over the practice of government. This article aims to address the management of village finances based on legislation, the factors that make corruption prevention important, and the role of the community in corruption prevention through legal training for cadres in Galang Suka Village, Deli Sedang Regency. This study uses normative and empirical legal research that is expected to produce academic studies that are useful for governance, especially in the prevention of corruption in Galang Suka Village, Deli Sedang Regency. This research is conducted in two stages. First, conducting a study of normative law. Second, conducting a study on the implementation of regulations on village financial management. The results of the study indicate that the Deli Serdang Regency Government has implemented several policies, including a large budget allocation, fixed income and allowances for the head and village officials. The factors that cause corruption in village funds are the lack of community involvement in the planning and supervision of village funds. Community participation in overseeing the use of village funds is one of the keys to the success of utilizing village funds.

Keywords: Legal Training, Formation of Legal Cadres, Corruption Prevention Efforts

1. Introduction

1.1 Introduce the Problem

The village, as part of the government, has the authority to regulate and manage the interests of the community based on diversity, participation, indigenous autonomy, democracy, and community empowerment. The government is currently paying close attention to rural development. Based on Article 72 paragraph 1 letter b of Law No. 6 of 2014 on Villages, the government has provided billions of rupiah in funding to address the development gap in villages. However, the large amount of funds allocated to villages will not be managed properly if the human resources in the village, especially the village head and its apparatus, are not given proper

understanding, ultimately resulting in new corruptors. It is not impossible that corruption cases, which have recently affected many regional heads in several regions in Indonesia, could also affect village heads and other village officials.

In 2020, the Galang Suka Village in Deli Serdang Regency became a public discussion. According to news from NusantaraPosOnline.com, the head of Galang Suka Village, Deli Serdang, North Sumatra, was suspected of corruption in the BUMDes (Village-Owned Enterprises) fund. For almost three years from 2016-2019, the BUMDes fund was unclearly disbursed. The BUMDes fund comes from government funding in the amount of IDR 205,700,000, which was given in 2016 (NusantaraPos, 2020).

To prevent such incidents from recurring, it is necessary for the village head and village officials to receive guidance that clean and corruption-free governance is not only the responsibility of state officials, but also the responsibility of the community. Community participation is needed to conduct social control over the practice of government. This is in line with Article 82 paragraph 2 of Law No. 6 of 2014, which states that village communities have the right to monitor the implementation of village development (Cahyana, 2021).

In order to carry out the work and achieve the goals of the government that have been planned, supervision is needed. The purpose of supervision is to create a clean and authoritative apparatus supported by an effective and efficient government management system, as well as constructive and controlled participation of the community in the form of objective, healthy, and responsible social control (Situmorang, 1994).

Implementation of community surveillance can be carried out by individuals, groups, or organizations in the following ways:

1. Providing information regarding indications of corruption, collusion, or nepotism in the village government or BPD environment.
2. Providing opinions and suggestions for improvement, both preventive and repressive, on the issues (Triwulan & Widod, 2011).

The enactment of Law No. 14 of 2008 on Public Information Disclosure by relevant agencies is expected to open up public space for matters related to activities in the village. This freedom of public information is expected to make the government more transparent and free from negative actions such as corruption and nepotism.

Public disclosure of information gives wide attention to the people to participate in public policy and become a force in overseeing the development process of the region in Indonesia, including in the village. As stated in Article 1 paragraph 12 of Law No. 6 of 2014 on Villages, Village Community Empowerment is an effort to develop independence and prosperity of the community by increasing knowledge, attitudes, skills, behaviors, abilities, awareness, and utilizing resources through the establishment of policies, programs, activities, and appropriate assistance that reflect the essence of problems and priorities of village communities.

Community participation in law enforcement can be done individually or through community organizations in various activities such as:

1. Attending education about the consequences of corruption and knowledge related to activities in the village;
2. Avoiding ignorance towards corrupt practices in the surrounding environment, by actively monitoring the process of activities held in the surrounding environment related to the government and the village by reporting any suspicious activities;
3. Exercising control over various public policies (Ndraha & Uang, 2018).

Therefore, the initial step that can be taken is by providing education through programs from the government in collaboration with legal education experts in the form of training and formation of legal cadres, so that the rural community can exercise their rights and obligations to participate in monitoring the performance of the village government in implementing development projects using state funds. This will help establish good synergy between the village government and the community.

1.2 Explore Importance of the Problem

Preventing corruption at the village level is crucial because corruption at this level can have a very detrimental impact on society. Corruption can reduce the quality of public services provided by the village government and harm the community members who need assistance from the village government. Corruption can also harm the village's finances and cause the village budget that should be used for development and community welfare to be wasted.

Therefore, it is important to take preventive measures against corruption at the village level, one of which is through training and the formation of legal cadres. Through training and the formation of legal cadres, the community at the village level can gain a better understanding of the law and good governance, which can help the community understand what is expected from the village government and how the village government should act to avoid corruption (Habaora et al., 2020).

In addition, training and formation of legal cadres can help increase public awareness about the importance of preventing corruption and encourage active participation in monitoring and controlling the government. This can help the community carry out their roles as watchdogs and controllers of the village government more effectively, thus preventing corrupt practices.

However, efforts to prevent corruption at the village level are not enough with only training and formation of legal cadres. Other efforts are needed, such as transparency and accountability of the village government, as well as active participation of the community in monitoring and controlling the government. Furthermore, efforts to prevent corruption at the village level must be carried out systematically and sustainably, and must be supported by the village government and other relevant institutions (Pahlevi, 2022).

By conducting efforts to prevent corruption at the village level, it is hoped that a clean and corruption-free government can be created, as well as improve the quality of public services provided by the village government to the community. This will have a positive impact on the welfare of the people and better development at the village level.

1.3 Describe Relevant Scholarship

Nugroho focus on emphasizing the importance of training and forming legal cadres to prevent corruption at the village level (Nugroho, 2016). Asri dan Susanti, focuses on the model of corruption prevention at the village level through training of cadres (Asri & Susanti, 2016). Rahmawati dan Asri focuses on evaluating the effectiveness of anti-corruption cadre training in preventing corruption at the village level (Rahmawati & Asri, 2019). Basrowi dan Handoyo focuses on the model of forming anti-corruption cadres in preventing corruption in villages. (Basrowi & Handoyo, 2017). Yusuf focus on increasing community participation in corruption prevention at the village level (Yusuf, 2017).

1.4 State Hypotheses and Their Correspondence to Research Design

The hypothesis proposed in the research on preventing corruption at the village level through the training and formation of legal cadres is that such training and formation can be effective in preventing corruption at the village level. This hypothesis is in line with the research design that uses a quantitative approach by collecting data through surveys and statistical analysis to test the relationship between variables. In this research, the independent variable is the training and formation of legal cadres, while the dependent variable is the level of corruption at the village level. The research can also use a qualitative approach by conducting interviews or case studies to gain a deeper understanding of how training and the formation of legal cadres can help prevent corruption at the village level. In addition, the research can use a mixed methods approach that combines quantitative and qualitative approaches to obtain more comprehensive results.

2. Method

The research method used is normative juridical and empirical juridical, so that secondary data will be accompanied by primary data obtained directly from field observations through interviews and questionnaire distribution, which is expected to result in useful academic studies for governance management, especially in preventing corruption in Galang Suka Village, Deli Sedang Regency. The descriptive method can be interpreted as a problem-solving procedure that investigates by describing the condition of the subject or object in the study, which can be individuals, institutions, communities, and others that currently exist based on visible facts or as they are (Irwansyah, 2020).

2.1 Identify Subsections

This research is conducted in several stages. In the first stage, a study is conducted on normative law. The second stage involves a study on the implementation of regulations regarding village financial management. Therefore, this research requires both secondary and primary data (Sunggono, 1997). Primary data in legal research refers to data obtained mainly from empirical research, which is research conducted directly in the community of Desa Galang Suka. Data collection techniques are carried out through interviews, questionnaire distribution, and observation. Interviews are conducted by conducting in-depth interviews directly between the researcher and informants to obtain useful information in collecting data. Questionnaires are conducted by creating a list of systematically arranged questions and then distributed them to respondents to obtain useful information for the research. Observation is carried out by observing the phenomenon of the development of the financial governance of Desa Galang Suka.

2.2 Tipologi Penelitian

This legal research has a typology of normative empirical research. Normative empirical legal research (applied) examines the implementation of positive legal provisions factually in every particular legal event. The purpose of such examination is to ensure whether the results of the application of the law in concreto are in accordance with the provisions of the law. Normative empirical legal research consists of two stages. The first stage examines the existing regulations, and the second stage looks at how the implementation of those regulations takes place. This legal research has a juridical-empirical approach. Empirical legal research is research obtained directly from the community or by studying primary data (Efendi & Ibrahim, 2016).

2.3 Data Sources

The data used consists of primary and secondary data. Primary data are obtained directly from the research location, while secondary data are obtained from official documents, books related to the research object, research results in the form of reports, theses, dissertations, and legislation regulations.

2.3.1. Primary Legal Materials

Primary legal materials are authoritative legal materials, meaning they have authority. Primary legal materials consist of legislation, official notes or minutes in the making of legislation, and court decisions. The primary legal material used in this research is Law No. 31 of 1999, as amended by Law No. 20 of 2001 on the Eradication of Corruption.

2.3.2. Secondary Legal Materials

Secondary legal materials are legal materials that provide explanations of primary legal materials, namely the works of legal experts in the form of books, journals, research results, and opinions of scholars. The purpose of secondary legal materials is to provide researchers with guidance on where to go next (Marzuki, 2005).

2.3.3. Tertiary Legal Materials

Tertiary legal materials are legal materials that support primary and secondary legal materials, including the Indonesian Dictionary (KBBI), legal dictionaries, news articles, and qualitative data analysis whose results will be described in a descriptive analytical manner.

3. Results

3.1. *Factors Leading to the Importance of Corruption Prevention*

The amount of village funds received and managed by the village government must be a concern for various parties in the village to jointly supervise and manage them in accordance with applicable laws and regulations. This is further reinforced by the increasing number of corruption cases related to village funds in Indonesia. Indonesia Corruption Watch (ICW) found that the most cases of corruption enforcement by law enforcement officials (APH) occurred in the village budget sector, with 154 cases in 2021 and a potential state loss of Rp 233 billion. Corruption in village fund budgets had even tended to increase since 2015, when there were only 17 cases with a loss of Rp 40.1 billion. ICW recommends that supervisors in the village budget sector be closely monitored given that the central government allocated a village fund budget of Rp 68 trillion in 2022. In terms of actors, generally the perpetrators of corruption are village heads. The number of village heads who become suspects indicates that they did not carry out their obligations as stipulated in the Village Law. Article 26 paragraph (4) of the Village Law states that village heads are obliged to implement the principles of accountable, transparent, professional, effective, efficient, clean, and free from collusion, corruption, and nepotism in village governance.

From ICW's observation, seven common forms of corruption are identified that are generally committed by village governments, namely embezzlement, misuse of funds, abuse of authority, illegal levies, markups, fictitious reports, budget cuts, and bribery. These seven forms of corruption indicate that there are five vulnerable points in the village fund management process, namely: 1. Planning process, 2. Accountability process, 3. Monitoring and evaluation process, 4. Implementation process, and 5. Procurement process of goods and services in the distribution and management of village funds (Prakoso, 2019).

1. Some of the monitored modes of misusing village funds include:
2. Creating a budget plan with inflated prices above the market value.
3. Justifying the financing of physical buildings with village funds even though the project is sourced from other funds.
4. Temporarily borrowing village funds for personal purposes but not returning them.
5. Extorting or deducting village funds by officials from the subdistrict or district.
6. Creating fictitious official trips for the village head or officials.
7. Inflating the payment of honorarium for village officials.
8. Inflating the payment of office supplies.
9. Collecting village taxes or fees but not depositing the collection to the village treasury or tax office.
10. Purchasing office inventory with village funds but intended for personal use.
11. Cutting public budget then allocating it for the benefit of village officials.
12. Manipulating projects funded by village funds.
13. Creating fictitious activities or projects that are charged to village funds.

The factors causing corruption in village funds are varied. The most fundamental factor is the lack of involvement of the community in the planning and supervision of village funds. In practice, access for the community to obtain information on the management of village funds and to actively participate in planning and management is limited. However, Article 68 of the Village Law has regulated the rights and obligations of the village community to access and be involved in village development. Community involvement is the most fundamental factor because the village community knows the needs of the village and directly witnesses the development in the village (Safitri, 2022).

3.2. The Role of the Community in Corruption Prevention through the Formation and Training of Legal Cadres

The increasing corruption of village funds must be addressed by finding solutions to prevent it. If not, village corruption will continue to increase and disrupt the agenda of village development and welfare. In order to prevent village corruption from continuing and to achieve the goal of decentralizing authority and budget to the village, prevention efforts need to be made through strengthening formal and non-formal oversight functions. The participation of the community in oversight is believed to be the most effective, so it is important to ensure its implementation. In this case, the commitment of the village government in providing access to information and space for community involvement is important to be carried out.

Community participation in overseeing the use of village funds is one of the keys to the success of utilizing those funds. As an important element in the entire process of development, the community must be able to participate in proposing and overseeing the development process with the aim of bringing the greatest possible benefits for improving the quality of life of the community, improving access to basic needs, and even fostering a sense of ownership towards every result of the development process.

Based on the infographic of the Galang Suka Village Budget for the year 2022 in Galang Subdistrict, Deli Serdang Regency:

Total Revenue	: Rp. 1,286,441,000
Financing	: Rp. 34,918,308
Total Expenditures	: Rp. 1,320,393,308

The shopping details for each field are as follows:

1.	Field of Government Administration	Rp. 477.151.618
2.	Development Sector	Rp. 308.179.490
3.	Field of Community Development	Rp. 7.300.000
4.	Community Empowerment	Rp. 204.308.200
5.	Disaster Management Field	Rp. 324.000.000

To assess the perception and level of understanding of the community regarding the importance of community participation in monitoring the management of village funds, researchers distributed questionnaires to 20 respondents and the results are as follows

Table 1: Community Residence Status

	F	%
Indigenous Peoples	14	70
Peoplaere immigrants	6	30
Sum	20	100

Figure 2. Graph of the Population Status of the Galang Suka Village Community

Out of 20 respondents from the community of Desa Galang Suka, 70% (14 people) are native to the village while 30% (6 people) are newcomers

Table 2: The Level of Intensity of Galang Village Likes to Organize Government Activities

	F	%
Often	13	65
Not Often	7	35
Sum	20	100

The Intensity Level of Galang Village Likes to Organize Government Activities

Figure 3: Graph of the Level of Intensity of Galang Suka Village in Conducting Government Activities

From 20 respondents of Galang Suka Village community, it was found that 65% (13 people) have the perception that Galang Suka Village frequently conducts government activities, while 35% (7 people) have the perception that Galang Suka Village does not frequently conduct government activities.

Table 3: Community Involvement in Activities Organized by Galang Suka Village

	F	%
Ever	15	75
Never	5	25
Sum	20	100

Community Involvement in Activities Organized by Galang Suka Village

Figure 4: Graph of Community Involvement in Activities Organized by Galang Suka Village

From 20 respondents of the community of Galang Suka Village, it was found that 75% (15 people) have been involved in activities organized by Galang Suka Village, while 25% (5 people) have never been involved in activities organized by Galang Suka Village.

Table 4: Types of Activities Participated by the People of Galang Suka Village

	F	%
Committee	3	20
Mutual Aid/Cleaning	5	33,3
Taruna Reef	5	33,3
Community Empowerment	2	13,3
Sum	15	100

Activities Participated by Galang Suka Village

Figure 5: Graph of the Types of Activities Participated in by the Galang Suka Village Community

From 15 respondents of the community of Desa Galang Suka who stated that they had been involved in activities organized by the village, it was found that the majority participated in community service/cleanliness activities, which is 33.3% (5 people), and youth organization (karang taruna) activities, which is also 33.33% (5 people). Around 20% (3 people) participated in committee activities, while 13.3% (2 people) were involved in community empowerment activities

Table 5: Community Knowledge About the Fund Allocation System for Galang Suka Village Activities

	F	%
Know	4	20
Not Knowing	16	80
Sum	20	100

Knowledge of the Community Regarding the Allocation System of Funds for Activities in Galang Suka Village

Figure 6: Community Graph Regarding the Fund Allocation System for Galang Suka Village Activities

From 20 respondents of the community in Desa Galang Suka, it was found that only 20% (4 people) knew about the allocation system of funds for activities in Desa Galang Suka, while the majority, which is 80% (16 people), did not know about the allocation system of funds for activities in Desa Galang Suka.

Table 6: The level of public trust regarding the management of Galang Suka Village funds

	F	%
Believe	5	25
Disbelief	8	40
Not Fully Believing Yet	6	30
Don't Know	1	5
Sum	20	100

The Level of Trust of the Community on the Management of Village Funds in Galang Suka Village

Figure 7. Graph of the Level of Community Trust Regarding the Management of Galang Suka Village Funds

Out of 20 respondents from the community of Desa Galang Suka, it was found that the majority of the community does not trust the management of Desa Galang Suka's funds, which is 40% (8 people), while 30% (6 people) do not fully trust the management of Desa Galang Suka's funds. A number of 25% (5 people) trust the management of Desa Galang Suka's funds, and 5% (1 person) stated that they do not know.

Table 7: Community Knowledge Regarding Corruption Cases Involving Village Officials

	F	%
Know	12	60
Not Knowing	8	40
Sum	20	100

Knowledge of the Community Regarding Corruption Cases Involving Village Officials

Figure 8: Graph of Community Knowledge Regarding Corruption Cases Involving Village Officials

From the 20 respondents of Desa Galang Suka, it was found that 60% (12 people) have knowledge about corruption cases involving village officials, while the remaining 40% (8 people) do not have knowledge about it.

Table 8: Community Perceptions Regarding Sanctions That Should Be Given to Village Officials Who Commit Misappropriation/Corruption of Funds

	F	%
Related Parties Legally Followed Up	2	60
Related Parties Terminated	3	15
Do not know	5	25
Sum	0	100

Public Perception Regarding the Appropriate Sanctions for Village Officials Who Embezzle Funds

Figure 9: Graph of Community Perceptions Regarding Sanctions That Should Be Given to Village Officials who commit Fund Fraud/Corruption

From 20 respondents in the Galang Suka village community, it was found that 60% (12 people) have the perception that the appropriate sanction for village officials who commit embezzlement/corruption of funds is that the relevant parties should be prosecuted, while 15% (3 people) believe that the relevant parties should be dismissed. A total of 25% (5 people) answered "don't know" when asked about their perception of the appropriate sanctions for village officials who commit embezzlement/corruption of funds.

Table 9: Community Efforts in Preventing Corruption in Galang Suka Village

	F	%
Efforts to prevent	8	90
Shut up/Don't Know	2	10
Jumlah	20	100

Community Efforts in Preventing Corruption in Galang Suka Village

Figure 10: Graph of Community Efforts in Preventing Corruption in Galang Suka Village

From 20 respondents in the Galang Suka village community, it was found that 90% (18 people) make efforts to prevent corruption in Galang Suka Village when they sense signs of fraud, while the remaining 10% (2 people) remain silent when corruption occurs in the village.

Table 10: Public Perception of the Interests of Youth/Youth Anti-Corruption Law Cadres as the Front Line in Corruption Prevention in Galang Suka Village

	F	%
Important	20	100
Not Important	0	0
Sum	20	100

Community Perception on the Importance of Youth Anti-Corruption Law Cadres as the Frontline in Preventing Corruption in Galang Suka Village

Figure 11: Graph of Community Perceptions Regarding the Interests of Youth/Youth Anti-Corruption Legal Cadres as the Front Guard in Corruption Prevention in Galang Suka Village

From 20 respondents in the Galang Suka village community, all respondents with a percentage of 100% (20 people) agreed on the importance of youth/teenage anti-corruption law cadres as the frontline in preventing corruption in Galang Suka Village.

Table 11: Views, Criticisms, Suggestions, and Inputs Related to Good Village Government Management

	F	%
Transparent Government	11	55
Allocation of Funds to the Community	2	10
Do not know	7	35
Sum	20	100

Opinions, Criticisms, Suggestions, and Inputs Regarding Good Village Governance Management

Figure 12: Graphic of Views, Criticisms, Suggestions, and Inputs related to Good Village Government Management

From 20 respondents in the Galang Suka village community, the majority of the respondents, amounting to 55% (11 people), believe that to produce good village governance management, the government should be transparent, while 10% (2 people) stated that funds should be allocated for the benefit of the community. A total of 35% (7

people) answered "don't know" when asked about their opinions, criticisms, suggestions, and inputs regarding good village governance management.

Table 12: Public Knowledge of Examples of Corruption

	F	%
Misappropriation of Village Funds	12	60
Data Manipulation	2	10
Money/Time Corruption	3	15
Bribes/Bribes	1	5
Do not know	2	10
Sum	20	100

Public Knowledge Regarding Examples of Corruption

Figure 13: Graph of Public Knowledge Regarding Examples of Corruption

In the graph above, it can be seen that more than 50% of community knowledge regarding examples of corruption is related to embezzlement of village funds with a value of 60% (12 people), followed by corruption of money/time 15% (3 people), data manipulation 10% (2 people), and bribery in the last position with a value of 5% (1 person). A total of 10% (2 people) answered "don't know" about examples of corruption.

Table 13: Public perception of the statement that corruption can hurt the people

	F	%
Get	20	100
Unable to	0	0
Sum	20	100

Public Perceptions of the Statement that Corruption Can Harm the People

Figure 14: Graph of Public Perceptions of the Statement that Corruption Can Harm the People

From 20 respondents in the Galang Suka village community, all respondents, with a percentage of 100% (20 people), agreed that corruption could cause suffering to the people

Table 14: Community Opinion on Village Interests Making Village Integrity Statement

	F	%
Necessary	10	50
Absolutely necessary	10	50
Sum	20	100

**Opinions of the Community on the Importance of
the Village Creating an Integrity Village
Statement**

Figure 15: Graph of Community Opinions Regarding Village Interests Making a Village Integrity Statement

From 20 respondents in the community of Galang Suka Village, 50% (10 people) have the perception that the creation of a village integrity statement is very necessary and 50% (10 people) stated that it is necessary. Community participation in overseeing the use of village funds is one of the keys to the success of utilizing these funds. The community, as an important element in the entire development process, must be able to take part in proposing and overseeing the development process with the aim of bringing the greatest possible benefit to improving the quality of life of the community, increasing access to basic needs, and even the community can maintain and foster a sense of ownership of every result of the development process. Article 24 of Law Number 6 of 2014 concerning Villages states that the implementation of Village government is based on the principle of participatory governance.

Barriers to community participation in village budget management include:

1. Unwise decisions, such as unfair and unequal distribution of village funds focused on one program and one village chief.
2. Non-interactive communication. Lack of communication between the government and the community in planning, decision-making, program implementation, and budgeting processes.
3. Lack of community awareness. The community is indifferent to what the government decides and does (apathetic) regarding budget management.
4. Low education. With low community education, the community does not know what to do regarding planning, implementation, and supervision of village budget use.
5. Lack of transparency and accountability. There is no transparency in the use of funds in program implementation and no accountability for the program implementation and budgeting processes.

From the questionnaire results, the majority of the Galang Suka Village community does not know the allocation system for village activities, meaning that the village government is not transparent, resulting in a low level of community trust in the local government. This is evidenced by the former Village Chief who was suspected of embezzling BUMDesa funds. This situation is being addressed by the newly appointed Village Chief, Mr. Drs. Suhelman, S.PD.I. In an interview with him to obtain input on community programs, he is not hesitant to go down and mingle with the community directly.

4. Discussion

The Village Law and its implementing regulations have mandated village governments to be more independent in managing their governance, including financial management and village assets. Some policies include allocating a large budget to villages and providing fixed income and allowances to village heads and officials. The Deli

Serdang Regency Government implements Law No. 6 of 2014 on Villages, Government Regulation No. 43 of 2014 on the Implementation of Law No. 6 of 2014, and Minister of Home Affairs Regulation No. 20 of 2018 on Village Financial Management by issuing Regent Regulation No. 3 of 2019 on Village Financial Management. The causes of village fund corruption can vary and be complex. Some factors that can contribute to village fund corruption include:

1. Limited knowledge and financial management skills of village officials.
2. Limited supervision and accountability for the use of village funds by authorized parties.
3. Political interests in managing village funds, such as using village funds for campaign purposes.
4. Lack of transparency in the management of village funds, such as not providing clear information on the use of village funds to the public.
5. Demands and pressures from the community on village governments to fulfill their needs.
6. Lack of community awareness of the importance of preventing corruption and overseeing village funds.

Therefore, efforts are needed to increase understanding and knowledge about village financial management, improve transparency and accountability, and involve communities in overseeing the use of village funds. In addition, it is also important to build strong awareness and commitment from village leaders and communities to prevent corruption and promoting good village financial governance.

Community participation in monitoring the use of village funds is one of the keys to the success of utilizing the funds. The community, as an important element in the entire development process, must be able to participate in proposing and monitoring the development process with the aim of bringing the greatest benefit to improving the quality of life of the community, increasing access to basic needs, and even fostering a sense of ownership towards every result of the development process.

Acknowledgments

This paper is an output of research funded by the Talent Research Fund organized by the USU research institution in 2022. Therefore, thanks are expressed for the assistance of various parties so that this article can be published.

References

- Asri, N. A., & Susanti, Y. (2016). Model Pencegahan Korupsi Pada Tingkat Desa Melalui Pelatihan Kader [Prevention Model of Corruption at the Village Level Through Cadre Training]. *Jurnal Ilmiah Mahasiswa Bimbingan Dan Konseling Universitas Negeri Malang*, 3(2), 1–9.
- Basrowi, B., & Handoyo, A. (2017). Model Pembentukan Kader Anti Korupsi Dalam Pencegahan Korupsi di Desa [Model for the Formation of Anti-Corruption Cadres in Corruption Prevention in Villages]. *Jurnal Studi Pemerintahan*, 8(1), 10–19.
- Cahyana, Y. (2021). Pembekalan Penggunaan Software dan Pemahaman Teknologi Untuk Perangkat Desa Di Desa Pasirukem [Provision of Software Usage and Technological Understanding for Village Devices in Pasirukem Village]. *Jurnal Ilmiah Pangabdhi*, 7(2), 72–75. <https://doi.org/10.21107/pangabdhi.v7i2.11211>
- Efendi, J., & Ibrahim, J. (2016). *Metode Penelitian Hukum: Normatif dan Empiris [Legal Research Methods: Normative and Empirical]*. Prenada Media Group.
- Habaora, F., Riwukore, J. R., Manafe, H., Susanto, Y., & Yustini, T. (2020). Strategi Pencegahan dan Pemberantasan Korupsi di Pemerintah Kota Kupang, Provinsi Nusa Tenggara Timur, Indonesia [Strategies for Corruption Prevention and Eradication in the City Government of Kupang, East Nusa Tenggara Province, Indonesia]. *Aspirasi: Jurnal Masalah-Masalah Sosial*, 11(2), 229–242. <https://doi.org/10.46807/aspirasi.v11i2.1556>
- Irwansyah. (2020). *Penelitian Hukum; Pilihan Metode dan Praktik Penulisan Arikel [Legal Research: Method Choices and Article Writing Practices]*. Mitra Buana Media.
- Marzuki, P. M. (2005). *Penelitian Hukum [Legal Research]*. Pranadamedia Grup.
- Ndraha, A. B., & Uang, D. P. (2018). Strategi Pemberdayaan Masyarakat Desa Melalui Pengembangan Ekonomi Lokal di Kabupaten Halmahera Barat Provinsi Maluku Utara [Empowerment Strategies for Village Communities through Local Economic Development in West Halmahera Regency, North Maluku Province].

- Jurnal Pembangunan Pemberdayaan Pemerintahan*, 3(2), 137–149.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.33701/j-3p.v3i2.867>
- Nugroho, R. (2016). Pencegahan Korupsi Pada Tingkat Desa Melalui Pelatihan dan Pembentukan Kader Hukum [Corruption Prevention at the Village Level through Training and Formation of Legal Cadres]. *Jurnal Ilmiah Mahasiswa Hukum Universitas Surabaya*, 5(1), 1–11.
- NusantaraPos. (2020). Dana BUMDes Desa Galang Suka Deli Serdang Ludes Diduga Disikat Kades [Funds of Village-Owned Enterprises (BUMDes) in Galang Suka, Deli Serdang Village Allegedly Embezzled by the Village Head]. NusantaraPos.
- Pahlevi, F. S. (2022). Strategi Ideal Pemberantasan Korupsi di Indonesia [Ideal Strategies for Combating Corruption in Indonesia]. *E-Journal Al-Syakhsiyah Journal of Law and Family Studies*, 4(1), 28–43.
- Prakoso, A. R. (2019). Efforts to Build Village Community Awareness in Supervising the Use of Village Funds. *L. Research Rev. Q*, 5(1), 123–134. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.15294/snh.v5i01>
- Rahmawati, E., & Asri, N. A. (2019). Efektivitas Pelatihan Kader Anti Korupsi Dalam Pencegahan Korupsi Pada Desa [The Effectiveness of Anti-Corruption Cadre Training in Corruption Prevention at the Village Level]. *Jurnal Ilmiah Mahasiswa Bimbingan Dan Konseling Universitas Negeri Malang*, 4(1), 1–9.
- Safitri, R. (2022). Analisis Penyalahgunaan Alokasi Dana Desa Oleh Kepala Desa (Studi Kasus di Desa Taman Jaya) [Analysis of Misuse of Village Funds Allocation by the Village Head (Case Study in Taman Jaya Village)]. *Jurnal Petitum*, 2(1), 45–55.
- Situmorang, V. M. (1994). *Aspek Hukum Pengawasan Melekat [Legal Aspects of Inherent Supervision]*. Rineka Cipta.
- Sunggono, B. (1997). *Metode Penelitian Hukum [Methods of Legal Research]*. PT Raja Grafindo Persada.
- Triwulan, T., & Widod, I. G. (2011). *Hukum Tata Usaha Negara dan Hukum peradilan Tata Usaha Negara Indonesia [State Administrative Law and Administrative Judiciary Law in Indonesia]*. Kencana.
- Yusuf, A. H. (2017). Meningkatkan Partisipasi Masyarakat Dalam Pencegahan Korupsi di Tingkat Desa [Enhancing Community Participation in Corruption Prevention at the Village Level]. *Jurnal Bina Praja*, 9(1), 19–28.